

HARMONY OF UNIVERSAL AND NATIONAL IDEAS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL CULTURES

Ochilova Nigora Ruzimuratovna

Karshi Institute of Engineering Economics
Associate Professor of the Department of Social Sciences (Uzbekistan
University of Information Technology and Management
Associate Professor of the Department of Pedagogy
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ABSTRACT

The national idea is becoming a moral foundation and a life program for every citizen on the path to building a free and prosperous Motherland, a free and prosperous life. It can be said objectively that after the achievement of independence, they "let go" of democracy in fear, telling their citizens and political subjects to "take democracy in your arms!" countries that tried to speed up the processes of social renewal were caught in the middle of various ethnic and religious conflicts, separatism, organized crime, and terrorism. This can be clearly observed in the case of the Russian state.

The main goal of the reforms implemented in Uzbekistan is to create decent living conditions for every citizen of our nation. This serves to make every citizen, regardless of nationality, understand the nature of the reforms implemented in our country and become an active participant in it. The national idea has its place in this.

In particular, the idea of a perfect person is a noble idea that has both a national and a universal essence, embodies the highest spiritual and physical perfection of a human being, and always motivates him to be good. Social cooperation is a philosophy of compromise, which ensures the unity of individuals and groups of different nationalities, races and religions towards a common goal. Therefore, for multi-ethnic Uzbekistan, the ideas of "people's well-being", "social cooperation" and "perfect person" are distinguished by the fact that they are directed to the goals and interests of all people and people, not the interests of any individual, group or nation.

National Cultural Centers have proven with their effective and active activities that they are social voluntary organizations of all nations and peoples living in Uzbekistan in the field of culture, spirituality, national customs and traditions. In 1989, under the Ministry of Cultural Affairs of Uzbekistan, the Republican Inter-National Cultural Center was established in order to coordinate and harmonize their activities. Taking into account the growing number and types of activities of national cultural centers, on January 13, 1993, the Republican International Cultural Center was transformed into the Republican International International Cultural Center.

As a result, organizations became independent non-governmental institutions. In Uzbekistan, it serves to conduct national policy at the level of the requirements of a democratic state and civil society. In addition, it should be considered that the idea of national independence is inextricably linked with the material and spiritual aspects of people's daily life, lifestyle, well-being. A correct understanding of this by representatives of different nationalities helps to correctly understand the idea of national independence.

The idea of national independence expresses the priority goals and interests of the society of Uzbekistan.

In fact, the fact that representatives of each nation mobilize their intelligence to improve the welfare of the people in Uzbekistan is a unique wealth of the country. Uzbekistan's geographical and strategic opportunities and the use of rich natural raw materials require it. The changes taking place in the socio-economic life of Uzbekistan under the conditions of independence play an important role in the implementation of the tasks of building a democratic society based on market economy relations. For example, more than 2,700 different mineral deposits and promising places of ore have been identified so far. They include about 100 types of mineral raw materials. More than 60 of them are involved in production. More than 900 mines have been discovered, and their proven reserves amount to 970 billion US dollars. The republic ranks 4th in the world in gold reserves, 7th in mining, 10-11 in copper reserves, 7-8 in uranium reserves. Representatives of different nationalities use their potential in using them.

The national idea, by its essence, also reflects the tasks and goals that are related to the fate of the people and the nation, and which must be solved in the short or long term. The fact that the social character of our national idea is inextricably linked with the aspirations and needs of the people becomes wider and deeper only as a result of philosophical analysis. Therefore, on the eve of independence and in the first years of independence, a certain vital ground, need and later conditions were formed for our national idea. Only the national idea can be a flag and a program that unites the people.

The fruit of the creative activity of our people - our national idea serves to ensure that representatives of different nationalities and religious faiths work as a family in the way of creativity and creativity both politically, legally and morally. The most important thing is that our people are realizing their historical identity as a nation, are increasingly strengthening their "self-standing" status, and are trying to preserve their place in the world community and perpetuate this great place. "An idea that does not adhere to the trinity of national consciousness, national thinking, and understanding of national identity, does not reflect it, or is not directed to its development and strengthening, cannot claim the status of a national idea."

Republican International Cultural Center, 138 national cultural centers, friendship and cultural-educational relations between Uzbekistan and foreign countries based on the principles of preservation and comprehensive development of the history, culture, spiritual values, national traditions and customs of all nationalities and ethnic diasporas living in Uzbekistan the council of communication societies, as well as 34 friendship societies are successfully operating. Raising the culture of tolerance and humanitarianism in society, ensuring inter-national and inter-confessional solidarity, civil harmony, as well as strengthening friendly, equal and mutually beneficial relations with foreign countries are part

of the state policy of Uzbekistan.
is one of the priority directions.

In the first year of his presidency, the head of the republic, despite various predictions, tried to make the state more open, and the result of this is reflected in our daily life. All this, along with diplomatic efforts to improve relations with its neighbors, is creating a sense of confidence in the country at home and abroad about a previously unanticipated future, experts from Spain's old "think tank" said. The solution to the problem is the adoption and implementation of the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. The era we are living in today is a well-thought-out, mutual environment aimed at strengthening the independence and sovereignty of our country, creating an environment of security, stability and close neighborliness around the country. conducting a beneficial and practical policy, as well as further strengthening humanitarian values and mutual solidarity between representatives of different nationalities in the minds of the population, especially young people, and raising the quality of the work being carried out in this regard to a new level

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